

A comparison of Hierarchical Signal Detection Theory and Polytomous Item Response Theory

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Experimental Psychology

- Recognition Memory

Experimental Psychology

- Recognition Memory

Experimental Psychology

- Recognition Memory

Recognition Accuracy

- Corrected scoring
 - Subtract false alarms from hits

Number of Cues Recognized

Recognition Accuracy

- Corrected scoring
 - Subtract false alarms from hits

Recognition Accuracy

- Signal-detection theory

Recognition Accuracy

- Signal-detection theory (DeCarlo, 1998; 2010; 2011; 2012)

$$P(y = 1|S) = \Phi((\Psi_S - c)/\tau)$$

$$P(y = 1|N) = \Phi((\Psi_N - c)/\tau)$$

$$P(y = 1|X) = \Phi\left(\frac{\Psi_N - c}{\tau} + \frac{\Psi_S - \Psi_N}{\tau} X\right)$$

$$P(y = 1|X) = \Phi(-c + dX)$$

$$P(y_{ij} = 1|c_i, d_i, \alpha_j, \delta_j, \mathbf{X}) = \Phi\left(-c_i + d_i \mathbf{X} - (-\alpha_j + \delta_j \mathbf{X})\right)$$

Signal Detection Item Characteristic Curves

Psychometrics

- Ability assessments

Psychometrics

- Ability assessments

Psychometrics

- Ability assessments

Ability Estimates

- Score each cue separately
- Conditionalize on shared common stimuli
- True/False Rasch Testlet Model
$$P(y_{ij} = 1) = \Phi(\theta_i - t_j + \gamma_{d(j)i})$$
- Aggregate accuracy across cues that share common stimuli
 - Partial Credit Model

	Endorse	Ignore
Valid	1	0
Invalid	0	1

Signal-detection as a measurement model

- Two component processes underlying responding behavior
 - A latent trait underlies sensitivity to relevant information
 - A latent trait underlies endorsement bias
- How does the signal detection framework compare to polytomous IRT models?
 - Correspondence between candidate parameters?
 - True/False Testlet Model
 - Partial Credit Model

Simulation Study

Factor 1:
Sample Size

Factor 2:
Number of
Items

Factor 3:
Number of
Cues

Fitted
Model:

Generated Parameters

Candidate: Sensitivity $\sim N(0, 1)$ Bias = $-.3, 0, .3$	Items: Sensitivity $\sim N(0, 1)$ Bias $\sim N(0, .1)$
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100 ... 1,000 By 100

20 Items 30 Items 40 Items

4 Cues 6 Cues 8 Cues

Signal Detection

Partial Credit Model

Rasch Testlet Model

Simulation Study

Generated Parameters
Candidate: $\begin{pmatrix} d_i \\ c_i \end{pmatrix} \sim N \left[\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1^2 & .6 \\ .6 & .3^2 \end{pmatrix} \right]$

Factor 1:
Sample Size

100

...

1,000

By 100

Factor 2:
Number of
Items

20 Items

30 Items

40 Items

Factor 3:
Number of
Cues

4 Cues

6 Cues

8 Cues

Fitted
Model:

Signal Detection

Partial Credit Model

Rasch Testlet Model

Correlated Signal Detection Parameters

PCM Ability vs SDT Sensitivity: -.3 Bias

PCM Ability vs SDT Sensitivity: Neutral Bias

PCM Ability vs SDT Sensitivity: .3 Bias

PCM Ability vs SDT Sensitivity: Conditional Bias

Rasch Testlet Ability vs SDT Sensitivity: Conditional Bias

Rasch Testlet Ability vs PCM Ability

Results

- Polytomous IRT ability estimates are highly correlated with Signal Detection sensitivity estimates
 - $> .95$
 - Regardless of responding bias
 - Fixed
 - Conditioned on sensitivity
- Less variability in IRT ability estimates
- Parameter recovery
 - Diminishing returns after 400 Candidates and 20 items with 8 cues

Conclusion

- Signal Detection provides richer behavioral account of responding
- Isolates the source of recognition errors—sensitivity vs bias
 - Current polytomous IRT models cannot account for responding bias

THANKS

